

Off-axis holographic imaging with undetected light

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Abstract: Quantum imaging with undetected light (QIUL) leverages the quantum correlations of photon pairs generated via spontaneous parametric down-conversion (SPDC) to retrieve both amplitude and phase information of an object. This method enables illumination and detection at distinct wavelength ranges, utilizing advanced detection technology in the visible spectrum while probing the object at an exotic wavelength. Here, we experimentally demonstrate a QIUL technique incorporating Fourier off-axis holography within a hybrid-type induced-coherence nonlinear interferometer. Our approach reconstructs the amplitude and phase information of an object in a single shot using a wide-field configuration, presenting a viable alternative to multi-frame acquisition techniques such as phase-shifting holography.

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1. Introduction

Recent advancements in holographic imaging techniques have propelled their application across diverse fields such as manufacturing, in-line quality control [1,2], and medical research [3], particularly in the analysis of cellular and tissue structures. Among these techniques, quantitative phase imaging has emerged as a robust methodology [4,5].

Historically, various imaging approaches have been developed to study transparent organisms. Notable examples include phase contrast microscopy, pioneered by Zernike in 1932 [6], and a range of holography-based techniques introduced by Gabor in 1948 [7,8].

The quantum revolution has developed holographic imaging schemes by leveraging the quantum properties of light to surpass classical limitations. These innovations have significantly enhanced phase sensitivity [9–11], facilitated investigations into fundamental photon properties like amplitude and phase [12–17], and enabled the use of diverse wavelengths for both sample illumination and detection [18–21].

Non-linear interferometry has become indispensable in quantum optics, encompassing applications in quantum communication, imaging, sensing, and information theory [18,22–24]. These interferometers integrate parametric amplifiers and second-order non-linear crystals to generate photon pairs via SPDC, enabling precise control and manipulation of phase changes in the optical field [22,25].

QIUL merges principles from non-linear interferometry and quantum optics. By exploiting SPDC in a non-linear crystal pumped by a laser, QIUL generates spatially correlated photon pairs (signal and idler photons) whose wavelengths can be finely tuned by adjusting the pump and crystal parameters [25–28]. This method illuminates the sample with the idler beam at a specific wavelength, distinct from the detected signal beam, utilizing advanced silicon-based technology [26,29–31].

This work represents a significant advancement from earlier holographic techniques that relied on digital phase-shifting holography (DPSH) [20] and multiple images for reconstruction [32]. Our approach utilizes Fourier off-axis holography (OAH) [7,33,34], extracting both amplitude and phase information from a single image. By eliminating the need for a piezo stage to control interferometer phase, this method reduces system complexity and cost, thereby enhancing practical feasibility in various optical imaging applications.

2. Non-linear interferometer for quantum OAH

2.1. In-line and off-axis classical holography

Since its inception, holography has established itself as a fundamental technique widely employed across diverse fields, including microscopy, interferometry, security, and data storage [4,5,33]. In this section, we discuss two primary approaches in classical holography: in-line and OAH.

In classical holography, the amplitude of a laser beam is split in half through a 50:50 beam splitter (BS) positioned at the center of a Michelson-Morley interferometer, generating the object and reference beams [34,35] (see Fig. 1(a)). The object beam interacts with the sample and is back-reflected by a mirror placed at the end of the arm. Both beams recombine at the BS and are directed towards the camera plane to form the hologram. In-line holography extracts object information when the object and reference beams spatially overlap with a relative angle of zero. In contrast, in OAH, a relative angle between the object and reference beams is introduced, typically through the tilt of a mirror, thereby introducing a linear phase shift to the reference beam [33–36].

In-line holography is conventionally implemented through DPSH, which requires at least three measurements to retrieve the amplitude and phase information carried by the optical field [32]. One drawback of this technique is its limitation in studying samples whose dynamics change over timescales comparable to or shorter than the duration of one measurement cycle. OAH represents an alternative requiring only a single measurement to reconstruct the amplitude and phase carried by the field. Furthermore, this method offers a robust stability against changes in the laboratory conditions such as temperature fluctuations and mechanical vibrations [33,34,36], therefore enabling the study of dynamic behavior within a shorter time window compared to DPSH. These contrasting methodologies differ in how the interfering intensity components are distributed in the Fourier space (FS). Figures 1(b) and 1c illustrate the relative angle between the object and reference beams and its impact on the distribution of their intensity components in the FS.

Let us introduce the intensity distribution of the OAH recorded at the camera plane [34–36]:

$$I(\mathbf{r}) = |E_O(\mathbf{r}) + E_R(\mathbf{r})|^2 = |E_O(\mathbf{r})|^2 + |E_R(\mathbf{r})|^2 + E_O^*(\mathbf{r})E_R(\mathbf{r}) + E_R^*(\mathbf{r})E_O(\mathbf{r}). \quad (1)$$

The components of Eq. (1) are derived from the squared coherent sum of the object and reference fields. The first two terms correspond to the squared amplitude of the object field $E_O(\mathbf{r})$ and the reference field $E_R(\mathbf{r})$, respectively. The third and fourth are the interference terms that depend on the relative phase between them, the asterisk denotes complex conjugation.

Taking the Fourier transform (FT) of Eq. (1) results in:

$$\tilde{I}(\mathbf{q}) = DC(\mathbf{q}) + \tilde{E}_O^*(\mathbf{q}) \otimes \delta(\mathbf{q} - \mathbf{k}) + \tilde{E}_O(\mathbf{q}) \otimes \delta(\mathbf{q} + \mathbf{k}), \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1. Comparison between in-line and OAH (upper row) and classical and quantum OAH (lower row). (a) A coherent beam is directed into a Michelson-Morley interferometer. The beam incident on the object is tilted relative to the reference beam, causing the +1, DC, and -1 diffraction terms to separate in the FS, as depicted in (b) and (c). (d) Classical implementation of OAH. (e) Quantum implementation of OAH, the purple beam pumps the non-linear crystal in forward and backward direction, generating signal and idler beams via SPDC in both directions. A relative angle is introduced between object and reference beams, which recombine at the BS and interfere at the camera plane to produce a hologram.

where the tilde denotes FT with respect to position \mathbf{r} , \otimes signifies linear convolution, and \mathbf{q} denotes spatial frequency. The first term is the auto-correlation term, which is the FT of the first two terms of Eq. (1), while the second and third terms are the direct and conjugate terms, respectively. These last two terms exhibit a displacement proportional to the wavevector \mathbf{k} , usually carried by the reference beam, $E_R(\mathbf{r}) = A_R e^{i\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{r}}$, where A_R is its amplitude. They are often referred to as the +1 and -1 diffraction orders, respectively. In DPSH, due to the full spatial overlap between the object and reference beam, this splitting does not occur, as shown in Fig. 1(b). The wavevector \mathbf{k} is introduced in OAH with the sole purpose of splitting the first-order terms relative to the zero order in the FS, shown in Fig. 1(c), allowing the direct term to be filtered and isolated to obtain a complex-valued image through an inverse Fast Fourier Transform (IFFT). The modulus corresponds to the amplitude $A_O(\mathbf{r})$ and the argument value corresponds to the phase $\phi_O(\mathbf{r})$ of the object field [14,34,35]. The wavevector \mathbf{k} is proportional to the relative angle between the object and reference beams, controlled mechanically, such as by tip-tilt adjustment of mirrors.

The characteristics of quantum off-axis holography adhere to classical principles, where increased relative angles correspond to higher fringe density within the hologram or equivalently to shorter spatial periods of the fringe pattern. The direction of the fringe's orientation is determined by the axis in which the +1 and -1 diffraction terms open in the Fourier space which is controlled by the tip-tilt of the mirror mount. When a systematic and controlled tip-tilt is introduced, the fringe period changes along this direction regardless of how long or short the spatial frequency is. Further elaboration is provided in Section 2.2.

2.2. Classical vs quantum off-axis holography with undetected light

The fundamental principles of classical holography extend to its quantum counterpart, where the hologram is formed through the interference of object and reference beams [7]. The distinction

lies in the nature of these beams. In classical holography, the object and reference beams are derived from a coherent laser beam split by a beam splitter [34,35], as illustrated in Fig. 1(a) and (d). These beams coexist simultaneously, overlapping spatially and temporally at the camera plane.

In contrast, quantum off-axis holography with undetected light (QOAHUL), depicted schematically in Fig. 1(e), involves a coherent purple beam pumping a non-linear crystal bidirectionally to generate photon-pairs via SPDC [29,30]. The forward generated signal beam (cyan beam with red dashed line) serves as the object beam, its idler twin beam interacts with the object and is back-reflected to the crystal. The backward-generated signal beam acts as the reference beam (cyan beam with black dashed line), its idler twin beam overlaps spatially with the forward generated idler at the crystal plane to induce coherence on their signal beams [37,38]. This coherence allows for interference at the camera plane.

In the low-gain regime, only one photon pair is typically generated at any given time, resulting in a hologram observed at the camera plane formed by the interference of probability amplitudes associated with the generation of the object and reference beams, which never directly interact with the object [14,39].

In QOAHUL, interference between the object and reference beams occurs due to coherence induced by the spatial and temporal overlap of their twin idler beams within the coherence time of the pump beam [37,38,40]. This overlap ensures the absence of which-path information; the observer cannot distinguish whether the signal photon detected at the camera plane originated from the forward or backward path, resulting in a single-photon interference pattern [37,38,41,42]. Reconstruction of object information is facilitated by spatial correlations inherent in the photon-pair, specifically momentum correlations stemming from momentum conservation in the SPDC process [27,39]. Furthermore, the undetected light scheme allows operation in distinct wavelength ranges for illumination and detection, leveraging mature silicon-based detection technologies in the visible spectrum [26,29,30].

2.3. Experimental setup

Figure 2 depicts the implemented setup for QOAHUL. A periodically poled potassium titanyl phosphate (ppKTP) non-linear crystal, 2 mm in length, is pumped by a continuous-wave laser at 405 nm with an output power of 20 mW, yielding signal photons at 910 nm and idler photons at 730 nm through SPDC. The purple-colored pump beam propagates bidirectionally within the ppKTP crystal, creating two distinct probability amplitudes associated with photon-pair generation events in both directions [29,39]. These events are assumed equally probable.

In the forward path, where photon-pairs are generated, the cyan signal beam and red idler beam are separated using an off-the-shelf dichroic mirror (DM-1). The idler beam, along with the pump beam, is further split by DM-2, allowing the idler beam to traverse a configuration resembling a Michelson-Morley interferometer. Upon reaching the end of the interferometer arm, the idler beam interacts with the object before being reflected back to the crystal by a mirror, where it spatially overlaps with the idler beam generated in the backward direction. Proper alignment of these beams induces coherence in their respective signal counterparts, enabling interference at the camera plane [37,38]. Two long-pass spectral filters with a 442 nm cut-off wavelength are used to block the pump power, and a band-pass filter with a central wavelength of 900 nm and a bandwidth of 32 nm is employed.

Both forward and backward signal beams propagate through the lower and upper arms of a Mach-Zender interferometer (MZI), respectively. Introduction of a relative angle between object and reference beams is achieved by slight tip-tilting of the mirrors immediately before the beam splitter (BS), as discussed in Section 2.1 [34–36]. The MZI configuration facilitates precise control of optical path differences between the beams, allowing for large relative angles that enhance the imaging capabilities of the system [34,35].

Fig. 2. A 2 mm long ppKTP non-linear crystal is excited by a continuous-wave laser operating at 405 nm. The crystal generates photon pairs via SPDC in both forward and backward directions, resulting in signal and idler beams at wavelengths of 910 nm (cyan) and 730 nm (red), respectively. While the signal beam does not interact directly with the object located in the idler path, it plays a crucial role in the process of image reconstruction.

Despite never directly interacting with the object, the signal beam facilitates image reconstruction due to induced coherence and spatial correlations between signal and idler beams [27,37].

At the camera plane, the signal beams generated in both the forward and backward directions, referred to respectively as the object and reference beams, generate a single-photon hologram, the intensity distribution of which can be computed as

$$I(\mathbf{r}) \sim 1 + \cos^2(\theta) + 2T^2(\mathbf{r}) \cos(\theta) \sin[\phi + \phi_{\text{tilt}}(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r}) + 2\phi_{\text{object}}(\mathbf{r})], \quad (3)$$

where θ represents the relative angle between object and reference beams, ϕ denotes a global interferometric phase controlled experimentally, $\phi_{\text{tilt}}(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ indicates a linear phase dependent on the relative angle between object and reference beams induced by mirror tip-tilt. $\phi_{\text{object}}(\mathbf{r})$ denotes the spatially varying phase and $T(\mathbf{r})$ denotes the spatially dependent transmission function of the object. The square and the factor of 2 account for the double-pass through the object [14,18,29,43].

In the current configuration, momentum correlations are utilized [27,44]. Lenses L1 - L5 and L7, each with a focal length of 150 mm are positioned to project the Fourier Plane (FP) of the crystal onto the object plane, the rightmost mirror, and the BS as depicted in Fig. 2. Lens L6, with a focal length of 75 mm, images this projected FP onto the camera plane with a 1:1 magnification. This setup enables the utilization of photon-pair momentum correlations to reconstruct an image by detecting a photon that did not interact with the object.

3. Methods and results

3.1. Image reconstruction road map

Figure 3 shows sequential images obtained during the reconstruction process, based on classical OAH [2,34–36]. Initially, the hologram, Eq. (3), is recorded using a sCMOS camera with $6.5 \mu\text{m}$ pixel size, an exposure time of 6 seconds and zero gain. The field of view spans a diameter of $11.9 \pm 0.1 \text{ mm}$. The raw image depicts the single-photon hologram exhibiting a high spatial modulation in the light-blue highlighted area due to the introduced relative angle between the object and reference beams. This modulation includes slight fringe distortions caused by the presence of the phase object. Next, the raw image is treated in the FS by taking its fast Fourier transform (FFT). Zooming into the yellow highlighted region reveals the +1, DC and -1 terms

characteristic of the Fourier OAH. Subsequently, the direct term (+1), enclosed within the dashed black circle, is cropped and centered while maintaining the original image dimensions (2048 x 2048 pixels). This region undergoes an IFFT resulting in a complex-valued image. The modulus of this image corresponds to the amplitude, while its argument represents the phase of the optical field probing the sample, yielding amplitude and phase images [34,35]. A reference image of a glass plate devoid of object features is previously recorded, and its phase image is subtracted from the image containing the object features to calibrate the system. Finally, the phase of this resulting image is unwrapped to achieve a flat and uniform phase distribution, which is presented as the final image [33,36].

Fig. 3. Image reconstruction process, proceeding from left to right. The single-photon hologram is initially captured at the camera plane, followed by a detailed examination of the blue highlighted region showcasing the characteristic high fringe density inherent to OAH schemes. Subsequently, a FFT is applied to the hologram, revealing the +1 term within the black dashed circle in the zoomed-in view of the yellow square. The direct term is isolated, centered, and maintained at original image dimensions. An IFFT is then executed to derive amplitude and phase images. A reference phase image is acquired and subtracted from the image containing object features, facilitating subsequent phase unwrapping to achieve the final phase image.

3.2. Imaging capabilities of QOAHUL

To evaluate the imaging capabilities of the optical system, we conducted a comprehensive study focusing on phase contrast variation with exposure time, spatial fringe density influence on overall image quality, and spatial resolution assessment. These measurements are essential in imaging schemes to validate the system performance, optimize parameters, ensure reliable image reconstruction and to assess the impact of artifacts.

For characterization purposes, we utilized various objects. Firstly, the standard binary object from the 1951 United States Air Force (USAF) resolution target is employed (Fig. 4(a)), with its corresponding amplitude image depicted in Fig. 4(b).

A second object consisted of a glass plate featuring a miniaturized version of the USAF resolution target. The reconstructed phase image acquired with a 9-second exposure time is presented in Fig. 4(c).

Additionally, a glass plate engraved with letters "IOF" is used. The corresponding reconstructed phase image, acquired with a 6-second exposure time, is displayed in Fig. 4(d). Both phase objects, with a refractive index of 1.6, are employed to validate the efficacy of our technique. The

Fig. 4. Imaging capabilities of QOAHUL. (a) Image of the standard 1951 United States Air Force (USAF) resolution target, (b) amplitude image of the USAF target, (c) phase image of the USAF phase object, (d) phase image of the glass plate with engraved IOF letters, (e) and (f) height profiles of the USAF and IOF phase objects corresponding to the features indicated by white lines in (c) and (d) respectively, (g) amplitude image of a fly-wing; the white bar denotes a length of 1.6 mm.

physical height estimation of the engraved features corresponding to the white lines in Fig. 4(c) and Fig. 4(d) is shown in Fig. 4(e) and Fig. 4(f), respectively. Our measurements closely align with manufacturer data, with values of 189 ± 7 nm for the USAF object and 182 ± 1 nm for the IOF object. Finally, the system's resolution capabilities are sufficient to discern features of a fly-wing, as illustrated in Fig. 4(g) with its amplitude image.

3.2.1. Phase contrast vs exposure time

To determine the minimum exposure time required for the optical system to retrieve the phase contrast of the USAF phase object, we systematically varied the exposure time from 0.5 s to 9 s. Figure 5(a) depicts the amplitude images of the USAF phase object in the upper row, while the lower row shows phase images corresponding to the region highlighted by the yellow square in Fig. 4(c). The area enclosed by the black dashed rectangle in the lower row of Fig. 5(a) is selected for phase contrast analysis.

Phase contrast calculation proceeds as follows: First, the average phase value within the dashed black square region of the lower row of Fig. 5(a) is determined and used as a threshold to distinguish between signal (above threshold) and background (below threshold), resulting in separate images for each. Second, the average value and standard deviation are computed for both signal and background images. Third, phase contrast is defined as the difference between the average signal and background phases, with its standard deviation determined by the sum of the squares of the corresponding standard deviations of the signal and background images.

With increasing exposure time, the capability of the system to reconstruct object features improves. Clear distinction of object features is achieved after 1 s of exposure. Figure 5(b) demonstrates strong agreement between our measurements and the expected phase contrast value, averaging around 1.95 radians (manufacturer specification) from 1 s to 9 s. Significant deviation is observed at the 0.5 s integration time, where the system fails to reconstruct the object due to a low signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). The resulting images exhibit higher noise levels, insufficiently suppressed by the current signal, leading to phase fluctuations and scrambled images as depicted in Fig. 5(a) for the 0.5 s exposure time.

Fig. 5. Phase contrast versus exposure time. (a) The amplitude and phase images of the USAF phase object are displayed in the upper and lower rows, respectively. From left to right, the images correspond to exposure times of 0.5, 3, 6, and 9 seconds. A gradual improvement in image quality is observed with increasing exposure time. (b) Exposure time is varied from 0.5 to 9 seconds. For exposure times between 1 and 9 seconds, the phase contrast remains approximately at the expected value of 1.95 radians, as specified by the manufacturer. The regions enclosed by the black dashed rectangles in all images are used for phase contrast analysis.

Enhancements in SNR and integration time could be achieved by employing a more powerful laser and/or extending the crystal length [26]. In our setup, the pump power is 20 mW with a 2 mm crystal, yielding an estimated photon flux of $3.7 \cdot 10^6$ photons/mW/s reaching the camera plane.

3.2.2. Phase contrast vs spatial period of the fringe pattern

The influence of the relative angle between the object and reference beams on the phase contrast and overall image quality is investigated. This angle affects the separation of the +1 and -1 terms in the FS, as described in Eq. (2). A narrow angle impedes the filtering and isolation of the direct term, thereby degrading image quality by incorporating spatial frequency components of the DC term. Conversely, a wider angle facilitates the filtering and isolation of the direct term. However, the angle has an upper bound determined by the pixel size of the camera, given by $\theta_{\max} = \sin^{-1}(\lambda/2d)$. Assuming the small angle approximation (when $\lambda \ll d$), the maximum angle is approximately $\theta_{\max} \sim \lambda/(2d) = 4^\circ$, where λ is the detected wavelength (910 nm) and d is the pixel size (6.5 μm). While this angle estimation is subject to errors due to the broad bandwidth of the SPDC spectra, it provides a useful reference.

Measuring this relative angle directly is challenging due to the spatial distribution of the SPDC spectra. Thus, a practical approach to evaluate this angle is through the spatial period of the fringe pattern. These values are calculated from the hologram images, in which the spatial period is measured directly from the fringe patterns, this was done by localizing the center of two

continuous dark or bright fringes. The larger the spatial period, the harder is to localize its center, resulting in larger errors. Figure 6 illustrates the influence of the fringe pattern spatial period on the image quality of the optical system, with all images captured at a 9 s exposure time.

Fig. 6. Influence of the fringe pattern spatial period on amplitude and phase images of the USAF phase object. (a) The upper row presents close-up views of single-photon holograms, where bright and dark fringes are distinctly visible, with the spatial period decreasing from left to right. The middle and lower rows show the corresponding amplitude and phase images, respectively. An optimal balance between contrast and the number of fringes is observed at a spatial period of $\Lambda = 113 \pm 1 \mu\text{m}$. (b) The spatial period of the fringe pattern is varied from $63 \mu\text{m}$ to $255 \mu\text{m}$. For shorter spatial periods, the measurements closely align with the expected phase contrast values. The regions enclosed by black dashed rectangles are utilized for phase contrast analysis in all images.

First, close-ups of the single-photon holograms are shown in the upper row of Fig. 6(a). From left to right, the spatial periods of the dark and bright fringes are: $\Lambda = 255 \pm 7 \mu\text{m}$, $\Lambda = 113 \pm 1 \mu\text{m}$, and $\Lambda = 63 \pm 3 \mu\text{m}$.

A long spatial period impedes the system's ability to retrieve object information, despite relatively good fringe visibility, as shown in the first column of Fig. 6(a). A long spatial period corresponds to a small relative angle, causing the direct and conjugate terms to not separate sufficiently from the DC component. This leads to fewer spatial frequency components of the object being captured, resulting in poor image quality, as explained in Sec. 2.1 and Fig. 1(c).

On the other hand, a very short spatial period does not guarantee optimal performance due to low fringe visibility, as seen in the third column of Fig. 6(a). In this scenario, a shorter spatial period indicates a larger relative angle between the sample and reference beams. This increased angle reduces fringe visibility due to the loss of path indistinguishability.

Figure 6(b) analyzes the effect of the spatial period on phase contrast. Large deviations occur at longer spatial periods, where the +1 and DC terms overlap in the Fourier space, making suitable reconstruction unfeasible. The greatest deviation occurs at $\Lambda = 213 \mu\text{m}$, we believe this is caused by an abrupt phase jump at the edge of the dashed black region of the lower row of Fig. 6(a). The phase jump is most likely caused by the influence of the reference image in the image reconstruction process. The graph suggests a minimal impact of the fringe spatial period on phase contrast.

The horizontal error bars on Fig. 6(b) are assessed as follows: the spatial period parameter is derived from the hologram images. Ten values of the spatial period are extracted to compute both their mean and associated uncertainty. These measurements are obtained from an area near the region where the fringes are distorted by the presence of the phase object. The vertical error bars are determined using the methodology outlined in Sec. 3.2.1.

3.2.3. Spatial resolution

The spatial resolution of the optical system is quantified using the modulation transfer function (MTF), $MTF = \frac{\pi}{4} * CTF$, where CTF denotes the contrast transfer function given by $CTF = \frac{I_{\max} - I_{\min}}{I_{\max} + I_{\min}}$ [45,46]. Figure 7 represents the MTF values derived from the amplitude (Fig. 4(b)) and phase (Fig. 4(c)) images of the USAF objects, acquired with a 9 s exposure time and a fringe pattern spatial period of $\Lambda = 113 \pm 1 \mu\text{m}$.

A spatial frequency is considered resolvable if its MTF values for both horizontal and vertical bar patterns, including uncertainties, exceed 0.09 for amplitude objects and 0.27 for phase objects. According to the Rayleigh criterion [28,31,47], the optical system resolves a spatial frequency of 5.6 lines/mm, corresponding to a feature size of $89 \mu\text{m}$ for both amplitude and phase objects.

For Fig. 7, error bar analysis is performed using phase-unwrapped images. Vertical and horizontal bar elements 1 to 6 are analyzed. Phase values for CTF calculation are obtained from 5 evenly spaced cuts across each bar element, extracted from rows (or columns for horizontal bars) containing phase data. Maximum and minimum values from these cuts are used to compute the CTF, which in turn determined the MTF. Average MTF values and standard deviations are then calculated based on the 5 measurements per bar element.

For the USAF amplitude object, all elements up to the second element of group 3 with horizontal bar patterns are resolved. Conversely, for the USAF phase object, all elements with vertical bar patterns are resolved, indicating a spatial frequency of 8.8 (lines/mm) and a feature size of $56.8 \mu\text{m}$. Variations in MTF values between horizontal and vertical oriented bar patterns may be attributed to slight tilts and shifts of the object plane from its nominal position along the optical axis.

Fig. 7. The USAF resolution target mask and phase objects serve as benchmarks to evaluate the spatial resolution of the optical system. Figure 4(b) and 4(c) are analyzed to compute the modulation transfer function (MTF) of the system. Elements of the USAF target, vertical and horizontal bar patterns, for which the MTF values (including their errors bars) are above the dashed horizontal lines are considered resolvable.

4. Discussion

We introduce a novel imaging method, QOAHUL, which combines a hybrid-type induced-coherence non-linear interferometer with classical OAH principles. This technique extracts both amplitude and phase information from objects by leveraging quantum correlations of photon pairs generated via SPDC. Unlike previous implementations [26,29,30], our method retrieves complete object information with a single measurement, enabling analysis of dynamic systems.

Our approach features a hybrid-type induced-coherence non-linear interferometer for OAH. Here, signal beams traverse a Mach-Zender interferometer, while idler beams pass through a Michelson-Morley interferometer [24]. This configuration enhances control over signal beams compared to bidirectional methods, where signal beams recombine post-reflection by a mirror at the crystal plane rather than at the beam splitter, omitting the Mach-Zender interferometer. Such bidirectional approaches impose strict constraints on relative beam angles and reduce fringe contrast due to distinguishability loss, thus compromising overall system performance. During the preparation of this manuscript, we became aware of a parallel study showcasing the bidirectional scheme [48].

The main limitations of bidirectional methods include the requirement for large transverse dimensions for the crystal and pump beam to ensure that the reflected idler beam overlaps with the pump beam in the non-linear crystal. This presents a technical challenge dependent on the transverse dimensions of the crystal and reduces photon-flux density per pixel. Consequently, they preclude the use of small-aperture non-linear crystals, as the laterally shifted idler beam would otherwise clip the crystal aperture before reaching a sufficient angle to split the diffraction terms in the FP. Most crystals utilized in QIUL are periodically poled and feature smaller aperture sizes (around 1 mm²), in contrast to BBO crystals (around 25 - 100 mm²), cited in [48]. Moreover, by using small cross-section periodically poled crystals provide access to higher nonlinearity, thereby improving signal-to-noise ratio by enhancing SPDC photon-flux.

The results outlined in Section 3 show the capability of the QOAHUL system in retrieving amplitude and phase information of the USAF resolution target mask and phase objects. However, some limitations are observed in the accuracy of the data, primarily due to abrupt phase jumps across phase images.

To enhance data accuracy, mitigating these abrupt phase jumps is essential. Increasing the separation between the DC and +1 terms in the Fourier plane can improve error bars by capturing higher spatial frequency components. Additionally, obtaining a reliable reference image by translating the object to a featureless region ensures consistency and reduces errors from inhomogeneity and laboratory conditions. Better control over sample positioning is also crucial, as horizontal bar patterns exhibit fewer phase jumps than vertical ones, likely due to alignment respect to the illumination beam. Thus, precise sample placement and optimized Fourier plane separation are key to improving measurement accuracy.

Our findings represent a significant advancement in holography, contributing to the evolution of holographic techniques based on non-linear interferometers with induced coherence. This innovation marks a leap forward in fields such as quantitative phase imaging and phase contrast microscopy.

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Data availability. The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, J.R.L.T., upon reasonable request.

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